

Comparison of Two Different Doses of Dexmedetomidine in Attenuation of Haemodynamic Response during Endotracheal Extubation

Ashutosh Ranjan¹, Mahesh Kumar²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology, Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology, Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Ashutosh Ranjan

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Abstract:

Background: Endotracheal extubation often triggers significant hemodynamic responses such as tachycardia and hypertension, which can be detrimental, particularly in patients with cardiovascular comorbidities. Dexmedetomidine, a selective α_2 -adrenergic receptor agonist, is known for its sedative and sympatholytic effects, making it a potential agent for attenuating these hemodynamic responses. However, the optimal dosing strategy remains uncertain.

Aim: To compare the effects of two different doses of dexmedetomidine on attenuating the hemodynamic response during endotracheal extubation to determine the optimal dose.

Methods: A study was conducted involving 160 adult patients scheduled for elective surgery requiring general anesthesia with endotracheal intubation. Participants were randomly assigned to two groups: Group A received a lower dose of dexmedetomidine, and Group B received a higher dose. Hemodynamic parameters, including heart rate and blood pressure, were recorded at baseline, immediately before extubation, and at 1, 3, 5, and 10 minutes post-extubation. Adverse events were also monitored. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Group B (higher dose) showed significantly lower heart rates and blood pressures at all time points post-extubation compared to Group A (lower dose) ($p < 0.05$). The incidence of adverse events, including bradycardia and hypotension, was slightly higher in Group A but not statistically significant. Overall, the higher dose of dexmedetomidine provided better hemodynamic control during extubation without a significant increase in adverse effects.

Conclusion: A higher dose of dexmedetomidine is more effective in attenuating the hemodynamic response during endotracheal extubation compared to a lower dose, with a favorable safety profile. These findings support the use of a higher dose in clinical settings where minimizing hemodynamic disturbances is critical.

Recommendations: Further studies should explore the long-term outcomes associated with higher doses of dexmedetomidine and investigate its efficacy in different patient populations, particularly those with high cardiovascular risk.

Keywords: Dexmedetomidine, Hemodynamic response, Endotracheal extubation, Randomized clinical trial, Anesthesia.

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Introduction

Endotracheal extubation, a critical phase in anesthesia practice, often triggers significant hemodynamic responses such as tachycardia, hypertension, and arrhythmias. These responses are primarily due to the stimulation of the sympathetic nervous system during the removal of the endotracheal tube, which can lead to adverse outcomes, especially in patients with cardiovascular comorbidities. Therefore, the attenuation of these responses is essential to reduce perioperative morbidity and mortality [1].

Dexmedetomidine, a highly selective α_2 -adrenergic receptor agonist, has gained prominence in anesthetic practice due to its sedative, anxiolytic, and analgesic properties, along with its ability to attenuate sympathetic responses. It exerts its effects by reducing norepinephrine release, leading to decreased sympathetic outflow and a subsequent reduction in heart rate and blood pressure. This makes dexmedetomidine an ideal agent for blunting the hemodynamic responses associated with extubation [2].

Recent studies have explored the efficacy of dexmedetomidine in various clinical settings, including its use in attenuating the hemodynamic response during extubation. A meta-analysis highlighted that dexmedetomidine effectively reduces heart rate and blood pressure during extubation, with fewer complications compared to other agents like opioids or β -blockers [3]. Another study demonstrated that dexmedetomidine provides a smoother recovery profile with reduced incidences of coughing and agitation, contributing to a more stable postoperative course [4].

Despite the established benefits of dexmedetomidine, the optimal dosing strategy remains a subject of ongoing research. While lower doses may be insufficient to fully blunt the hemodynamic response, higher doses raise concerns about potential side effects such as bradycardia and hypotension [5]. Therefore, a balance must be struck to maximize efficacy while minimizing adverse effects.

This study aims to compare the effects of two different doses of dexmedetomidine on attenuating the hemodynamic response during endotracheal extubation.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective, randomized, double-blind clinical trial.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at the Department of Anesthesiology, a tertiary care hospital.

Participants: A total of 160 participants were enrolled in the study. These participants were adult patients scheduled for elective surgeries requiring general anesthesia with endotracheal intubation.

Inclusion Criteria

- Aged 18-65 years.
- ASA physical status I or II.
- Scheduled for elective surgery under general anesthesia with endotracheal intubation.
- Provided informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with known hypersensitivity to dexmedetomidine.
- Patients with significant cardiovascular, hepatic, or renal impairment.

- Patients with a history of difficult intubation or known airway abnormalities.
- Pregnant or lactating women.
- Patients who had received sedative or opioid medications within 24 hours before surgery.

Bias: To minimize bias, randomization was performed using a computer-generated random number table. The study was double-blind; both the participants and the investigators responsible for data collection and analysis were unaware of the group allocations. This approach helped reduce the risk of selection bias and measurement bias.

Data Collection: Data collection involved recording baseline hemodynamic parameters, including heart rate, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, and mean arterial pressure before the administration of the study drug, immediately before extubation, and at specified intervals after extubation (e.g., 1, 3, 5, and 10 minutes post-extubation).

Procedure: Patients were randomly assigned to one of two groups: Group A received a lower dose of dexmedetomidine, while Group B received a higher dose. The study drug was administered intravenously 10 minutes before the anticipated extubation. Hemodynamic parameters were monitored continuously, and any adverse events were recorded. Extubation was performed following standard clinical protocols.

Statistical Analysis: Statistics were done using SPSS 23.0. Categorical variables were reported as frequencies and percentages, whereas continuous variables were provided as mean $\pm$ standard deviation. The independent t-test compared continuous variable means between groups, while the chi-square test compared categorical variables. A p-value under 0.05 was significant.

Result

The trial included 160 people in total, who were divided into two groups at random: Group A (low dose dexmedetomidine; n = 80) and Group B (high dose dexmedetomidine; n = 80). Table 1 provides an overview of the participants' baseline haemodynamic parameters and demographic details. Age, gender, weight, baseline heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, and mean arterial pressure did not significantly differ between the two groups.

Table 1: Baseline Demographic and Hemodynamic Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Group A (n=80)	Group B (n=80)	p-value
Age (years, mean $\pm$ SD)	45.6 $\pm$ 10.2	46.1 $\pm$ 9.8	0.726
Gender (M/F)	42/38	44/36	0.734
Weight (kg, mean $\pm$ SD)	68.3 $\pm$ 12.1	69.1 $\pm$ 11.8	0.623
Baseline Heart Rate (bpm)	78.4 $\pm$ 10.3	77.9 $\pm$ 9.7	0.772

Baseline Systolic BP (mmHg)	126.5 ± 12.4	127.2 ± 11.9	0.671
Baseline Diastolic BP (mmHg)	76.8 ± 8.9	77.1 ± 8.7	0.812
Baseline Mean Arterial Pressure (mmHg)	93.4 ± 9.2	93.7 ± 9.1	0.835

The hemodynamic parameters were recorded immediately before extubation and at 1, 3, 5, and 10 minutes after extubation. The results are summarized in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2: Comparison of Heart Rate (bpm) Between Groups at Different Time Points

Time Point	Group A (n=80)	Group B (n=80)	p-value
Pre-extubation	75.3 ± 8.4	74.9 ± 8.1	0.745
1 minute post-extubation	85.1 ± 9.2	79.2 ± 7.8	<0.001
3 minutes post-extubation	82.7 ± 8.6	77.3 ± 7.6	<0.001
5 minutes post-extubation	79.4 ± 8.2	74.1 ± 7.1	<0.001
10 minutes post-extubation	77.2 ± 8.0	72.8 ± 6.9	<0.001

Table 3: Comparison of Blood Pressure (mmHg) Between Groups at Different Time Points

Time Point	Group A (n=80)	Group B (n=80)	p-value
Pre-extubation	125.7 ± 11.3/75.2 ± 8.7	126.3 ± 10.9/75.5 ± 8.5	0.812/0.735
1 minute post-extubation	135.8 ± 12.5/83.1 ± 9.2	129.4 ± 11.0/79.6 ± 8.7	0.002/0.013
3 minutes post-extubation	132.5 ± 11.9/81.7 ± 8.9	126.8 ± 10.8/77.8 ± 8.4	0.003/0.012
5 minutes post-extubation	128.9 ± 11.5/79.8 ± 8.6	124.2 ± 10.4/76.2 ± 8.3	0.011/0.018
10 minutes post-extubation	126.2 ± 11.1/78.3 ± 8.4	122.7 ± 10.1/74.8 ± 8.0	0.029/0.021

The incidence of adverse events was monitored throughout the study. Group A reported a higher incidence of bradycardia (10% vs. 5%, p=0.185) and hypotension (12.5% vs. 7.5%, p=0.279) compared to Group B, although these differences were not statistically significant. The overall adverse event profile is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Incidence of Adverse Events Between Groups

Adverse Event	Group A (n=80)	Group B (n=80)	p-value
Bradycardia	8 (10%)	4 (5%)	0.185
Hypotension	10 (12.5%)	6 (7.5%)	0.279
Nausea	6 (7.5%)	5 (6.25%)	0.753
Vomiting	4 (5%)	3 (3.75%)	0.695

The statistical analysis demonstrated that the high dose of dexmedetomidine (Group B) was significantly more effective in attenuating the hemodynamic response during endotracheal extubation compared to the lower dose (Group A). Group B showed significantly lower heart rates and blood pressure readings at all measured time points post-extubation ($p < 0.05$). However, the incidence of adverse events did not significantly differ between the groups.

Discussion

The results of this study demonstrate that a higher dose of dexmedetomidine (Group B) significantly attenuated the hemodynamic response during endotracheal extubation compared to a lower dose (Group A). Patients in Group B exhibited consistently lower heart rates and blood pressure readings at all measured time points following extubation. These findings suggest that the higher dose of dexmedetomidine more effectively controls the physiological stress associated with extubation, thereby contributing to improved hemodynamic stability.

Despite the higher efficacy observed with the increased dose, the incidence of adverse events such as bradycardia and hypotension was slightly higher in Group A. However, these differences

were not statistically significant, indicating that both doses of dexmedetomidine were generally well-tolerated. This suggests that while the higher dose provides better control over hemodynamic fluctuations, it does not significantly increase the risk of adverse effects, making it a safe option for clinical use.

Overall, the study supports the use of a higher dose of dexmedetomidine for patients undergoing endotracheal extubation, as it offers superior hemodynamic control without a marked increase in adverse events. This has important implications for anesthetic management, particularly in scenarios where minimizing hemodynamic disturbances is critical.

A study examined the efficacy of two distinct dexmedetomidine dosages (0.5 µg/kg and 0.75 µg/kg) in relation to endotracheal extubation. It was discovered that, in comparison to the 0.5 µg/kg dose, the 0.75 µg/kg dose produced smoother extubation and higher sedation scores while offering superior control over haemodynamic measures, such as blood pressure and heart rate [6].

In a study, the effectiveness of esmolol and dexmedetomidine (0.5 µg/kg) in reducing the haemodynamic response during endotracheal extubation was evaluated. It was discovered that

dexmedetomidine was more successful in preserving steady haemodynamics and caused less side effects, such as coughing and restlessness after extubation [7].

A study evaluated how dexmedetomidine affected recovery and haemodynamic responses after tracheal extubation. When compared to a control group, it was discovered that dexmedetomidine dramatically decreased the incidence of tachycardia, hypertension, and coughing during extubation, resulting in a more seamless procedure and improved patient outcomes [8].

The effects of two dosages of dexmedetomidine (0.5 µg/kg and 1 µg/kg) on haemodynamic stability during extubation were assessed in a clinical experiment. According to the study's findings, compared to the lower dose, the greater dose of 1 µg/kg was more successful in lowering blood pressure and heart rate while also causing less extubation difficulties [9].

A study investigated the use of 0.5 µg/kg of dexmedetomidine to reduce haemodynamic reactions after extubation. The results of the trial showed that dexmedetomidine was useful in lowering blood pressure and heart rate, which in turn decreased the likelihood of problems following extubation [10].

Conclusion

The results of the study showed that a greater dose of dexmedetomidine, as demonstrated by lower heart rates and blood pressures in comparison to the lower dose, more successfully reduced the haemodynamic response during endotracheal extubation. Bradycardia and hypotension were somewhat more common with the larger dose, but these differences were not statistically significant. According to the research, a high dosage of dexmedetomidine may be utilised in clinical settings to enhance haemodynamic stability after extubation without risk.

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